

INDIVIDUAL APPROACH TO STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical conditions of working with students in an individual style in the course of music education.

Key words: Music education, individual approach, pedagogical activity, educational system, technology.

Students need to search and work independently, consider the given independent topics and tasks one by one. It is not for nothing that he independently prepares in other fields as well as in music. If we take the example of national musical instruments, i.e., orchestral ensembles, there are musical scores and parts, and it is necessary to memorize these musical notations. He should not blindly obey the instructions and opinions of his teacher, but he should be able to express his personal attitude on an issue through performance.

The lesson conducted under the guidance of a teacher is very important, but this does not negate the importance of the student's independent work, it is necessary to learn that the time spent on independent training of the student is not wasted. For this, it is necessary to explain to the student how to organize independent training and what to pay more attention to. Rational and productive use of time should be one of the principles of independent work.

One of the main principles is the regularity of training. It is necessary to form the skill of regular independent work in the student from the initial period of performance training. Usually, even if it is difficult to achieve regularity, it is desirable that such activities gradually become a habit. Some students repeat a given piece of music many times from beginning to end during independent practice. In this case, the meaning and specific features of the musical work are not fully and accurately analyzed. The work is superficially repeated only to be able to perform it in front of the student.

We also come across cases of some students being able to prepare homework. The reason for this is difficult to explain in one word. But in many cases, the reason why the homework is not ready is not because of the student's bad attitude towards the lesson or laziness, but because he does not fully understand the task and does not know how to approach learning a piece of music. Therefore, the task given for independent work should be explained to the student in detail and clarified taking into account the student's capabilities.

Another disadvantage of independent training is that students cannot control their own performance during task preparation. For example, when memorizing the text of a piece of music, a note is learned incorrectly, and the student himself does not notice it. Or a certain performance method is performed incorrectly, and this is also overlooked by the reader. Such a deficiency will be eliminated by the teacher during the lesson. The ability to control one's movements and the correctness of sounds during performance does not appear in students

by themselves, but is achieved through planned training. Self-control is very important for the performer, it is possible to eliminate shortcomings in the performance.

How should independent training be structured and what will it consist of? As we mentioned above, the clearer the task given for independent training, the easier the student's task. Regardless of how the independent training goes, it will give good results if it is carried out according to a certain plan. Below is the approximate structure and time of independent training:

1. 10-15 minutes of performing gamma, triads and various exercises.
2. It takes 15-20 minutes to learn a new task.
3. 5 minutes to rest.
4. Repetition of previously learned tasks 20-25 minutes.

The quoted times are approximate and are being determined taking into account the student's individual capabilities, the size of the tasks can be reduced or, on the contrary, increased. The total estimated time for independent training is 45-60 minutes. This may not seem like much at first glance. But if the exercises are continued regularly, the intended result can be easily achieved. Memorization of a piece of music is performed by each musician based on his abilities and capabilities. In this regard, it is difficult to have a single instruction for everyone. Some musicians have a stronger ability to remember the text by sight, while others have a stronger ability to remember it by hearing it. For this reason, their methods of memorizing the work are different. The important thing is that regardless of the method by which the piece of music is memorized, it remains firmly in the mind of the musician.

Currently, the increase in the amount of information to be assimilated in educational institutions requires achieving more results with less time. Bringing the class lesson closer to this independent activity under the guidance of the teacher will help the students' independent activities to be successful. In this case, the student performs all the tasks independently and the teacher gives his instructions only when necessary.

What time of the day should the teacher's independent training be? The timing of such training depends on the student's schedule. If the classes at the educational institution are mainly in the first half of the day, the independent training is held in the second half of the day, it is important that independent training is held at the same time every day.

There are a number of important aspects of doing homework that the student should remember. Let's consider some of them: First of all, the main task should be to correctly understand the musical work by the student, that is, to reveal the essence of the work correctly. As mentioned earlier, issues such as the choice of performance methods, observance of signs, and the correct placement of the applique are important for the correct understanding of the meaning of the work.

During the student's independent training, his attention must be focused on performing a specific task. Otherwise, the training will be meaningless and you will not be able to achieve any results. Some students pay more attention to the sheet music while learning a piece of music, forgetting that the performance should be expressive. In order to prevent this shortcoming, students should always focus on the task of expressive performance. In other words, students should pay as much attention to the expressiveness of the performance as they should spend on mastering the text of the work.

When the student makes a mistake, he should carefully repeat the passage at a moderate speed. Then he will correctly determine the cause of the mistake and take measures to

prevent it from happening again. Errors in students' performance also differ from each other. Repetition of certain situations has become a habit among students, and mistakes are repeated almost every time in a certain part of the work. The reason for this may be a correctly selected application, the method of execution, or another defect. Correct identification of the cause of such errors is the guarantee of its elimination. Even if the mistakes are accidental, they should not be allowed. Whatever the errors, the student should make it one of his main goals to find ways to eliminate them during his independent study.

As a result of playing an instrument, the student is both mentally and physically tired, so some time should be reserved for him to rest. Otherwise, the quality of performance will deteriorate, and errors and omissions may occur. It is known that people differ from each other in their individual characteristics. Just as there are no people with exactly the same characteristics, the characteristics of each student are also unique and unrepeatable. The requirements of education remain the same for all students. How to apply pedagogical tools to students to achieve effective results? Taking into account the individual characteristics of students in educational work, organizing work based on these characteristics can be an answer to the above question to a certain extent.

The problem of individual approach to students in the educational process has a creative nature. Each step of this process cannot be specified in advance. The issue of individual approach to students in pedagogy includes all stages of educational work. The essence of the individual approach is the implementation of the general educational task set before the student by pedagogical influence on each student, taking into account all his characteristics.

In practice, you can meet students with different behavior, character, and potential. Some students' abilities are noticed from a young age, while others take a long time to identify their abilities. Some students are cheerful, more playful and interested in many things, while others are calm and reserved. Regardless of the character and behavior of the students, they need the teacher's attention.

An individual approach to students is primarily focused on strengthening their positive qualities and eliminating their negative ones. If the teacher notices the negative qualities of the students and takes measures to eliminate them, it will prevent the difficult task of re-educating the student in the future. It is already known that it is useful to rely on the positive qualities of the student's character to increase the effectiveness of the individual approach in education. For example, let's say that a student learning a musical instrument is better developed than others, then it would be appropriate for the teacher to take into account the same qualities of the student when choosing a repertoire. This does not mean to ignore the less developed qualities in the student. On the contrary, effective use of positive qualities in students helps to use and perfect less developed qualities in them.

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